

COcyber Cybersphere Insights

April 2026

As we enter the last phase of the project, COcyber is bringing together a new set of outputs, insights, and opportunities for its community.

This edition highlights the **COcyber platform updates** related to **funding sources and guidelines**, the first two episodes from our **Cyber Duality: A Cocyber A podcast** series, and presents **two success stories** showcasing national use cases. It also invites members to take part in our community survey to gather feedback and help us shape future activities and tools around the needs of the COcyber network.

COcyber Platform Features

**EU funding
made simple**

Introducing Funding Sources:
Your shortcut to European investment.

[Click for opportunities](#)

The banner features a white background with green and blue abstract shapes. At the bottom, there are three logos: the European Union flag with the text 'Funded by the European Union', the COcyber logo, and the ECCC logo (European Cybersecurity Competence Centre).

Looking for cybersecurity funding opportunities in Europe?

The **COcyber Platform** includes a **dedicated funding sources** section that brings together major European and allied programmes supporting cybersecurity and dual-use innovation in one place.

It helps innovators, startups, SMEs, and research initiatives identify relevant opportunities, compare programmes, track deadlines, and access practical guidance for stronger applications.

Covering key 2026 opportunities, including Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, the European Defence Fund, EIC instruments, NATO DIANA, and the NATO Innovation Fund, it is designed as a gateway for anyone seeking to navigate Europe's cybersecurity funding landscape more effectively

[Click for opportunities](#)

How to Build a Winning Funding Proposal

Writing a strong cybersecurity funding proposal starts well before filling in an application form

A practical guide across EU Programmes, Accelerators & Funding Instruments for **cybersecurity dual-use technologies**.

- Step-by-step proposal writing strategies
- Insider tips from successful applicants
- Programme-specific guidance for Horizon, EDF, DIANA
- Common mistakes to avoid

[Download the funding guidelines](#)

Beyond funding, the COcyber Platform also includes features such as the **COcyber Map** (interactive overview of the EU cybersecurity landscape), the **Knowledge Base**, (central repository of curated resources and documents), the **Policy Coach** (AI-powered assistant providing support on cybersecurity policy questions), the **Projects Landscape** (interactive treemap with 87 EU-funded cybersecurity projects across Horizon Europe and Digital Europe) and the upcoming **Repository of Practices** and **Partner Research** sections.

[Join the COcyber Platform](#)

Cyber Duality: A COcyber Podcast

How do cybersecurity experts see the challenges, gaps, and future of cooperation between civilian and defence actors in Europe?

Cyber Duality: A COcyber Podcast brings together leading experts to answer this question. Each episode explores their experience, the challenges they face in practice, and how collaboration between sectors can be improved.

Through short, focused conversations, the podcast provides practical insights into real-world cybersecurity and highlights what needs to change to strengthen Europe's cyber resilience

[Fast Attackers, Slow Defenders: The Real Cybersecurity Imbalance](#)

In this first episode of **Cyber Duality: A COcyber Podcast** we explore how Europe can better connect civilian and defence cybersecurity efforts with insights from **Madhusanka Liyanage**, **Associate Professor and Ad Astra Fellow at University College Dublin**.

The discussion highlights key challenges such as fragmentation, limited knowledge-sharing, and regulatory complexity, while pointing to practical solutions like joint collaboration platforms.

[Listen to Episode 1](#)

[Strengthening Europe's Cybersecurity: Coordination, Innovation, and Sovereignty](#)

He discusses current **coordination gaps, strategic priorities**, and the role of the ECCC in **strengthening resilience, innovation, and technological sovereignty**.

In this second episode of **Cyber Duality: A COcyber Podcast**, **Luca Tagliaretti**, **Executive Director of the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC)**, shares insights from his work at the centre of Europe's cybersecurity ecosystem.

[Listen to Episode 2](#)

COcyber Success Stories

To understand **how cybersecurity ecosystems evolve across Europe**, [COcyber](#) conducted four national case studies focusing on Lithuania, Spain, Hungary, and Slovenia.

The studies, brought together in a [comparative booklet](#), examined:

- Governance structures
- Technology transfer
- Information-sharing mechanisms
- Dual-use cybersecurity potential

COcyber success stories: Spain case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer

Spain's case study evaluates how effectively the country transfers cybersecurity technologies & shares threat intelligence, examining governance structures, technology-transfer mechanisms, information-sharing practices, & the national landscape for dual-use cybersecurity deployment.

[Check Spain Success Story](#)

COcyber Success Story: Lithuanian case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer

Lithuania's case study examines how its NCSC-centred cybersecurity system functions, detailing national governance arrangements, defence-linked technology-transfer programmes, information-sharing systems, and the approach to deploying dual-use cybersecurity technologies.

[Check Lithuania Case Study](#)

COcyber Community Survey

Have you engaged with COcyber activities or events?

Share your feedback and help us improve. Tell us what works, what doesn't, and how we can make the community more relevant, useful, and connected.

[Link to the survey.](#)

Don't miss any future COcyber events connecting the dots between civilian and defence cyber security initiatives. Join our community now at <https://cocyber.eu/user/register>

This email has been sent to {{contact.EMAIL}}

You received this message because you are part of the COcyber Community.
We share updates on events, opportunities, and activities related to AI, cybersecurity, and European digital innovation

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